

Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-XII. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(2-substituted-benzalamino/benzoylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethoxy)diphenyl Sulphones

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p,p'-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (1) was treated with cyanogen bromide to get *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (2) which was condensed with different aromatic aldehydes/acid chlorides to get the corresponding benzalamino (3)/benzoylamino (4)-oxadiazole derivatives.

In view of the biological activity of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives¹ and in continuation of our earlier work², the synthesis of the 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives of type 3 and 4 was undertaken.

p,p'-Dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone on condensation with chloroacetic acid ester gave ester, which was then treated with hydrazine hydrate to get the hydrazide (1). 1 was treated with cyanogen bromide to get *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (2), which on condensation with different aromatic aldehyde/acid chloride gave the 2-benzalamino (3)/benzoylamino (4)-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been supported by ir and pmr spectral data (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of oxadiazole derivatives was carried out using cup-plate³ method at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus*

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 (SL. NOS. 1-16) AND 4 (SL. NOS. 17-35)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	Phenyl	176	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S
2.	4-Tolyl	118	76	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S
3.	2-Chlorophenyl	104	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₄ O ₆ S
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	138	82	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₄ O ₆ S
5.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	120	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S
6.	3-Aminophenyl	114	62	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ S
7.	4-Aminophenyl	128	68	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ S
8.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	146	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇ S
9.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	152	77	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇ S
10.	2-Methoxyphenyl	135	78	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₇ S
11.	4-Methoxyphenyl	164	82	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₇ S
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	132	80	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₈ S
13.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	148	79	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₈ S
14.	3-Nitrophenyl	182	82	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈ S
15.	Cinnamyl	110	52	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆ S
16.	4-Dimethylamino-phenyl	150	58	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆ S
17.	Phenyl	163	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S
18.	2-Methylphenyl	152	68	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S
19.	4-Methylphenyl	118	66	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S
20.	2-Chlorophenyl	132	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₄ O ₆ S
21.	3-Chlorophenyl	137	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₄ O ₆ S
22.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	104	59	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇ S
23.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	167	56	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇ S
24.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	220	58	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₈ S
25.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	160	54	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₈ S
26.	1-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl	174	66	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₇ S
27.	2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	215	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₇ S
28.	2-Methoxyphenyl	156	72	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₇ S
29.	4-Methoxyphenyl	142	68	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₇ S
30.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	155	76	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₈ S
31.	2-Nitrophenyl	265	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈ S
32.	3-Nitrophenyl	172	82	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈ S
33.	3-Pyridyl	170	56	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₆ S
34.	4-Pyridyl	196	64	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₆ S
35.	4-Bromophenyl	192	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ BrN ₄ O ₆ S

*N analysis found satisfactory.

aureus, *Staphylococcus citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasne serratia* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*.

The antimicrobial screening results showed that most of the compounds were moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi (10–20 mm, zone of inhibition). The maximum activity was observed in the 2-benzalamino-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (3) having R=4-methoxyphenyl against *A. niger*. In case of the 2-benzoylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4), maximum activity was observed in compounds having R=4-methylphenyl against *A. niger* and 4-pyridyl against *S. cerevisiae*. The activity is not comparable with the known antibiotic like chloromycetin and penicillin under similar condition.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A, 100.1 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

p,p'-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (1): An aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate (7 ml, 80%) was added to a suspension of *p,p'*-bis(carbethoxy methoxy)diphenyl sulphone (8.45 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (15 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h, cooled to room temperature, and the resulting solid was crystallised from DMF, (6.85 g, 87%), m.p. 228° (Found: C, 48.77; H, 4.57; N, 14.14. $C_{16}H_{18}O_6N_4S$ requires: C, 48.72; H, 4.60; N, 14.20%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 250 (C–O–C asym.), 1 145, 1 290 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1 680 (C=O) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH or NH_2); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.32 (4H, s, 2 × NH_2), 4.6 (4H, s, 2 × H_2COAr), 8.0–6.90 (8H, m, 2 × ArH); 9.4 (2H, s, 2 × CONH).

p,p'-Bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (2): A mixture of 1 (3.94 g, 0.01 mol) and cyanogen bromide (2.64 g, 0.025 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h at 50–60°. The reaction mixture was then cooled, neutralised with potassium bicarbonate solution, and the resulting solid was crystallised from dioxane–DMF (3:1) solvent, (3.37 g, 76%), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 48.64; H, 3.68; N, 18.88. $C_{18}H_{16}N_6O_6S$ requires: C, 48.64; H, 3.62; N, 18.91%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 250 (C–O–C asym.), 1 140, 1 290 cm^{-1} (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1 655, 1 105 (C=N and =C–O–C=, respectively of oxadiazole moiety), 3 275, 3 325 cm^{-1} (NH str. sym. and asym., respectively); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.92 (4H, s, 2 × H_2COAr), 5.30 (4H, s, 2 × NH_2) and 8.04–7.00 (8H, m, 2 × ArH).

p,p'-Bis(2-benzalamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (3): A mixture of benzaldehyde (1.01 g, 0.01 mol) and 2 (2.22 g, 0.005 mol) were refluxed in ethanol in presence of acetic acid (5–6 drops) on a water-bath for 6 h. The contents were then poured in cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol–dioxane (3:1)

solvent, (2.23 g, 72%), m.p. 176° (Found: C, 61.96; H, 3.90; N, 13.56. $C_{22}H_{24}N_6O_6S$ requires: C, 61.92; H, 3.89; N, 13.54%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 250 (C–O–C asym.), 1 145, 1 290 (–S=OH– asym. and sym., respectively), 1 660 (N=CH Schiff base), 1 685, 1 105 cm^{-1} (C=N and =C–O–C=, respectively, of oxadiazole moiety); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.72 (2H, s, 2 × CH=N), 4.94 (4H, s, 2 × H_2COAr) and 8.00–6.90 (18H, m, 4 × ArH).

Similarly, other aldehydes were condensed (Table 1; sl. nos. 1–16).

p,p'-Bis(2-benzoylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (4): A mixture of benzoic acid (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) and thionyl chloride (2.50 ml) in chloroform (20 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The excess thionyl chloride was removed by distillation and the acid chloride obtained was refluxed for 2 h with 2 (2.38 g, 0.005 mol) in chloroform (10 ml) in presence of pyridine (2–3 drops). The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol–dioxane (3:1) solvent, (2.32 g, 68%), m.p. 163° (Found: C, 58.82; H, 3.66; N, 12.81. $C_{22}H_{24}N_6O_6S$ requires: C, 58.88; H, 3.70; N, 12.87%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 250 (C–O–C asym.), 1 140, 1 295 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1 660, 1 105 (C=N and =C–O–C=, respectively, of oxadiazole moiety), 1 660 cm^{-1} (C=O, amide-I); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.80 (4H, s, 2 × H_2COAr), 5.28 (2H, s, 2 × CONH), 8.00–7.00 (18H, m, 4 × ArH).

Similarly, other aromatic acid chlorides were condensed (Table 1; sl. nos. 17–35).

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References

1. H. C. CALDWELL, R. J. SRIWALD and J. H. BURCKHALTER, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc., Sci. Ed.*, 1958, 47, 799; W. R. SHERMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 88; H. SAIKACHI, Br. Pat. 288 949/1964 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 60, 10692); J. METIVIER and R. BOESCH, Fr. Pat. 1 397 286/1963 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 60, 4157); E. JUCKER and A. LINDENMANN, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1962, 45, 2316; A. E. WILDERSMITH, E. FROMMEL and RADOUCO-THOMAS, *Arzneim-Forsch.*, 1953, 13, 238; B. HOKVÆLT and A. JOENSSON, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, 5, 247; Societe d'Exploitation des Laboratoires Jacques Logeais, Fr. Pat. M 1324/1962 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, 58, 1468); K. J. MEHTA, Ph D. Thesis, Saurashtra University, 1979; Y. INAZAWA, *Supporo. Med. J.*, 1952, 3, 48; G. BUCCOLATO, *Bull. Soc. Ital. Biol. Sper.*, 1955, 41, 986.
2. K. P. RODA, R. N. VANSADIA and H. PAREKH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 44.
3. F. KAVANAGH, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963, p. 126.